

European Cloud for Heritage Open Science

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Towards a distributed, multi-level, collaborative governance for Cultural Heritage Digital Commons

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List of Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
CH	Cultural Heritage
CIDOC CRM	CIDOC Conceptual Reference Model
ECCCH	European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage
EDIC	European Digital Infrastructure Consortium
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
GLAM	Gallery, Library, Archive and Museum
HDTO	Heritage Digital Twin Ontology
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
NGI	New Generation Internet
PPP	Public-private partnership
SME	Small and Medium-sized Enterprise
SRIA	Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda
TFEU	Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union

Abstract

ECHOES, the platform project for the Cultural Heritage Cloud initiative, is currently developing a governance model to implement its vision for a Cultural Heritage Digital Commons. This first policy brief reflects on discussions and ideas exchanged during two public policy events held in Brussels in 2024 and 2026.

To implement its vision, promote its values, and have a transformative effect on the field, future Cloud governance will need to successfully integrate multiple levels of cultural and digital governance, following the principle of subsidiarity; provide a platform for open participation by diverse stakeholders, and anticipate the field's evolution.

To do that, the Cloud should promote open norms, motivate their adoption by the community through user-driven approaches, and always ground them in shared values. The Digital Commons approach to governance provides value to stakeholders, empowers communities, increases resilience, and can support digital and cultural sovereignty within open science and open data paradigms.

Introduction

The European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage (ECCCH), also known as the Cultural Heritage Cloud, aims to support a comprehensive digital transition of a wide range of cultural heritage actors and stakeholders in line with Open Science principles and values.

Beyond state-of-the-art tools and infrastructure, this requires establishing a socio-technical network of institutions and actors that continuously produce new data and knowledge on cultural heritage within a shared digital space. This vision relies on three main concepts and related scientific and technical developments:

- Heritage Digital Twins, which provide access to the sum of all digital documentation related to a specific heritage asset.¹
- A digital continuum that allows the manipulation of digital heritage assets in a single environment by different actors.
- A community-led digital ecosystem of interoperable applications, tools, and services that connect with all the relevant European initiatives.

Together, they produce Cultural Heritage Digital Commons. This concept refers to open, accessible, and freely available digital data, tools and other resources that are collectively created, shared, and maintained by a federated community of professionals, researchers, and any other professionals in the field of digital cultural heritage.

Digital Commons play an important role in the structuration of online services and communities, as illustrated by Creative Commons and collaborative platforms such as Wikis, and have become a driving concept in EU digital policymaking, with inherent implications for participatory governance, transparency, and openness².

The production, exploitation, and use of cultural heritage data and related tools reflect the complexity of the current governance ecosystem, which is characterised by a complex repartition of roles and competencies among actors in the cultural and digital fields.

¹ Niccolucci F. *et al.* (2023) "The Heritage Digital Twin: a bicycle made for two", *Open Research Europe*.

² Krewer J. (2025) "From Open Access to Collective Governance – Two Decades of Digital Commons Policies in the European Union".

European Working Team on Digital Commons (2022) "Towards a Sovereign Digital Infrastructure of Commons", Report of the European Working Team on Digital Commons.

In this policy brief, we will investigate how Cultural Heritage Digital Commons data and tools can help shape the Cultural Heritage Cloud governance, and how they can translate into governance and policy recommendations for its stakeholders.

In particular, we will explore how this vision can be better implemented through a multi-level governance structure based on subsidiarity and meaningful interoperability, and Digital Commons can support digital and cultural sovereignty through democratised access, community empowerment and ethical governance.

This policy brief is based on the conclusions of two ECHOES Policy Events held in Brussels in December 2024 and February 2026. It complements the report on the Governance Model of the future Cultural Heritage Cloud legal entity, which recommends a two-step strategy to build a European Digital Infrastructure Consortium (EDIC).³

1. Reinforcing Subsidiarity with Cultural Heritage Cloud

The mission and vision of the Cultural Heritage Cloud put strong emphasis on collaboration between federated communities on open tools and knowledge about cultural heritage. Because cultural heritage is a shared responsibility that involves collaboration across several levels of governance and different types of actors (private, public, etc.), the Cultural Heritage Cloud must be able to interface with and mobilise a wide range of stakeholders to build Digital Commons.

To reach its full potential, collaboration must occur not only inside countries, governance levels, scientific disciplines, and sectors, but also between them. To achieve that goal, the Cultural Heritage Cloud and all like-minded partners must follow the general principles of European Union law, including proportionality and subsidiarity. These principles are particularly well-suited for the Cloud to implement Digital Commons, where the creators, owners, and users of cultural heritage data are represented and where communities have agency over their digital and cultural futures.

Digital cultural heritage is, by nature, both part of the digital and cultural sectors. While both sectors are undergoing change, the digital sector is currently undergoing a deep, rapid structural shift towards a platform- and AI-driven economy, which is affecting how the sector is governed at the different levels. The Cultural Heritage Cloud must use these

³ ECHOES (2026) *Governance Model of the legal entity (D10.2)*.

opportunities to help its community make the most of that change while defending its open science values.

1.1 Cultural heritage is a shared responsibility

Cultural heritage is a complex sector. Legal competences are distributed differently across countries, but beyond these legal arrangements, the social nature of cultural heritage makes us all responsible for it. Cultural heritage should be governed as a shared responsibility, requiring structured cooperation across institutions, stakeholders, and communities.

The Cultural Heritage Cloud governance principles⁴ reflect this necessity of joint responsibility and actively promote inclusiveness, stakeholder participation, and cross-sector collaboration to move beyond fragmented, siloed approaches and create Digital Commons. In this perspective, public authorities and institutions are expected to implement transparent and participatory mechanisms that enable co-creation, ensure equitable access, and reflect the collective value of cultural heritage.

a. Institutional level

At the institutional level, cultural heritage governance is carried out by public authorities, museums, research centres, and specialised agencies empowered by national law. These institutions are responsible for identifying, documenting, conserving, and promoting cultural heritage, as well as coordinating research, restoration, and public engagement initiatives. Their mandate typically includes developing inventories, managing collections, and advising policymakers on preservation priorities, ensuring that heritage is properly safeguarded and made accessible to the public.

Private companies, including small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), also play a crucial role in the study, conservation and valorisation of cultural heritage, and are often key contributors to the development of Digital Commons alongside public institutions, open-source communities and governments.

Institutions are the primary stakeholders of the Cloud. They provide and use data and resources. They participate directly in both the Cloud activities and its governance, either as future Members of the legal entity or through dedicated boards and participatory mechanisms.

⁴ Pollé, A., et al. (2025) *ECHOES Founding principles of the Cloud Governance (D10.1)*.

b. Regional authorities or local government level

Regional authorities often play a key role in managing cultural heritage, with significant variations based on their legal competencies as set out in their domestic constitutional and administrative frameworks. They integrate cultural heritage dimensions into spatial planning, regional development strategies, and educational programmes, while supporting local museums, archives, and heritage initiatives.

Regions and local governments support local innovation ecosystems and are often drivers to enable the digital transformation of local actors through investments in digital infrastructure and providing platforms for democratic, multi-level cooperation. These activities are often directly supported by national or European funding, such as the European Development Fund. Cooperation between different regional and local governments often adopts shared strategies and solutions within dedicated platforms, such as Eurocities.

Regional bodies and local governments are key partners to implement the European Collaborative Cloud for cultural heritage, in connection with local cultural heritage institutions, innovation ecosystems and citizens.

They will be formally invited to participate in the Cloud governance, either directly in the future legal entity, or through other formalised participation processes.

c. National level

In most countries, national authorities have primary legal competence over cultural heritage, including the adoption of heritage legislation, the designation and protection of monuments and historic sites, and the oversight of institutional structures responsible for implementation.

They ensure the establishment of clear conservation standards and responsibilities, including regulating conservation practices, allocating public funding, supervising professional practice in heritage management, and ensuring the integration of heritage considerations into broader cultural and territorial policies. National frameworks provide the legal and administrative foundation for the protection, promotion, and sustainable management of cultural heritage across the country.

National authorities play a central role in supporting the digital transition of institutions that produce, use or manage cultural heritage data, and the development of robust digital companies.

As large users and providers of data and resources, their support through policies, direct funding and procurement choices is often crucial to the success of Digital Commons.

National authorities are the primary decision-making level for the good implementation of the Cultural Heritage Cloud and its broader Digital Commons approach, and for synergies with national initiatives and activities.

The future General Assembly of the Cultural Heritage Cloud legal entity, its highest decision-making body, will give European Union Member States a majority of voting rights. Whenever relevant, national experts will also be invited to participate in boards and activities.

d. European level

Article 167 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (TFEU) establishes the legal framework for the European Union's role in the field of culture: the Union must contribute to the development of Member States' cultures while respecting national and regional diversity. Its intervention should focus on incentive measures, coordination, and support, without harmonisation of national laws (Article 167(5) TFEU), and must ensure that cultural heritage considerations are systematically integrated across relevant policy areas, in accordance with Article 167(4) TFEU.

Within that framework, the European Union has launched the Culture Compass for Europe, a new strategic framework for the EU's Cultural Policy. It also supports the development of the European Research Area in the field of cultural heritage through support to research projects and research infrastructures such as CLARIN ERIC, DARIAH ERIC and E-RIHS ERIC.

The European Union is playing a leading and transformative role in the establishment of Digital Commons across the world. The Digital Europe Programme (including the data space for cultural heritage), the European Open Science Cloud, and the proposed shift towards an Open Digital Ecosystem Strategy all position Europe as a key enabler of the field's transformation. These policies feed into the development of the Cultural Heritage Cloud.

i. European Commission

The European Commission operationalises EU cultural policy through implementing powers derived from Article 167 TFEU, ensuring coordination, funding allocation, and strategic guidance. Key policy instruments include the Work Plan for Culture 2023-2026 (Council Resolution 2022/C 466/01) and the Culture Compass for Europe, released in November 2025, which replaces the 2018 New European Agenda for Culture as the overarching strategic framework. The Culture Compass embeds culture across EU action and structures cultural governance around four axes directly relevant to data space, EOSC, and Cloud governance: culture for people, culture for artists and cultural professionals, culture for the planet, and culture for co-creative partnerships. This framing positions cultural heritage institutions as legitimate stakeholders in European research infrastructure governance and reinforces the case for high-level participation in shared data governance frameworks.

The European Commission provides key strategic frameworks within the fields of Culture, Digital transformation, and research. Through direct, project-based support, it contributes to the development of the Cultural Heritage Cloud, and, by doing so, to the reinforcement of Cultural Heritage Digital Commons

To continue its coordination, support, and harmonisation work on cultural heritage data, collaborative tools and resources, the European Commission will be invited to participate in the governance of the future legal entity.

ii. Data and research infrastructures

Research and Technology Infrastructures, such as the European Research Infrastructure Consortia (ERICs), are developed and supported within the Horizon Europe programme (Articles 179–190 TFEU on the European Research Area), while Data Infrastructures, such as the Common Data Spaces, are developed within the Digital Europe Programme (Article 173 TFEU).

These infrastructures are both users and providers of cultural heritage data and resources, or other generic services of interest for the cultural heritage community. Their governance must ensure interoperability, data sharing and long-term accessibility, in line with the Data Governance Act (Regulation (EU) 2022/868).

The involvement of existing European Research and Data Infrastructures in the future governance of the Cultural Heritage Cloud is a core feature of the ECHOES vision.

While the detailed mechanisms for their participation in the future governance structure are still under discussion on a case-by-case basis, the Cultural Heritage Cloud aims to provide a space for improved synergies among all actors of the Digital Commons and to improve the uptake of existing resources.

e. Umbrella organisations

Umbrella organisations play a central role in fostering participatory and multi-stakeholder governance. Within their own thematic and/or geographical boundaries, they facilitate coordination, representation, needs identification and knowledge exchange across the sector, in line with participatory principles promoted by the Council of Europe and reflected in EU policy frameworks such as the Work Plan for Culture 2023–2026, and the Cultural Compass for Europe released in November 2025, ensuring structured dialogue and stakeholder engagement. Several organisations exist both in the field of heritage, culture, open science and open data, and they are often key enablers of thematic Digital Commons.

Umbrella organisations also act as strong advocates for cultural heritage and open science, frequently serving as counsellors and advisors in policy-making processes. At the EU level, they contribute, for instance, to the work of the Commission expert group on cultural heritage, notably the Cultural Heritage Forum (E03650) established in 2019. Similar dynamics can be observed at the national level across various institutional frameworks. This advisory and advocacy role enables them not only to participate directly in policymaking but also to shape governance decisions more broadly.

This role is observable at the international level, where umbrella organisations such as ICOMOS directly participate in the international governance of cultural heritage. This level of governance provides a cooperative framework in which states retain primary discretion over heritage policies. While conventions adopted under UNESCO establish common standards, their implementation remains largely dependent on national or regional authorities. As such, international governance relies on coordination, soft enforcement mechanisms, and expert guidance, including contributions from umbrella organisations, rather than on coercive enforcement.

ECHOES recommends a similar approach to the inclusion of umbrella organisations as to research and data infrastructures within the future Cultural Heritage Cloud legal entity governance.

Umbrella organisations are essential partners to achieve meaningful community representation within the Cloud governance and to liaise with international actors. As such, they will be formally invited to participate in the governance structure and strategic planning.

1st Policy Recommendation

Structure the Cultural Heritage Cloud governance as a multi-level governance framework for Cultural Heritage Digital Commons

The Cultural Heritage Cloud should be established as a European Digital Infrastructure Consortium (EDIC) with a clearly defined multi-level governance framework that ensures coordination and complementarity between European, national, regional, and local levels.

Particular attention should be given to strengthening the role of regional and local actors, which are currently under-integrated despite their central role in cultural and innovation ecosystems.

Governance levels: EU, national, regional/local, institutional

1.2 Facilitating complementarity within and between levels

The current governance of cultural heritage and open science is complex and results from decades of evolution and transformation. The future Cultural Heritage Cloud governance should not add to the complexity of the distribution of competencies and responsibilities within the field. It should serve as an enabler of collaboration across levels and disciplines. The Cloud legal entity, which could take the form of an EDIC, will provide a meeting space for high-level dialogue between stakeholders within and between the different levels of governance of the field.

The ECHOES Consultation, together with other relevant work carried out by ECHOES and the ECCCH sister projects, shows that several fields within the category of “cultural heritage” are well integrated at the national, European, and international levels. However, this integration remains partial, context-dependent, and often siloed.

The future Cloud governance will need to address this issue through balanced, participatory mechanisms across stakeholder types and levels that, whenever possible, integrate existing representation mechanisms such as umbrella organisations or user associations. This is especially relevant in the field of research, where the Cloud should serve as a nexus for digital and research infrastructures that engage directly with cultural heritage, with a focus on their respective added value.

The **European Open Science Cloud** provides a framework for discipline-agnostic, research-driven tools and should serve as the Cloud’s reference partner for collaboration with other scientific disciplines and initiatives.

The **common European data space for cultural heritage** is an equally strategic partner, and, via the Europeana Initiative, has been a strong contributor to the development of cultural heritage governance. The [joint statement](#) published in March 2026 by the Europeana initiative and ECHOES on the complementarity of both initiatives marks a significant milestone in their partnership.

This statement includes shared commitments on interoperability, Intellectual Property Rights (IPR), design workflows, capacity building, governance, collaboration, and advocacy. In particular, it calls for establishing formal governance links between the Cloud and the data space. This commitment will be operationalised in the technical and strategic governance of the Cloud legal entity.

The EOSC and the data space for cultural heritage are large, complex, and multi-level initiatives that provide key contributions in establishing the Cultural Heritage Digital Commons. The Cultural Heritage Cloud can provide a platform to ensure they connect in a meaningful way and, through a virtuous circle, offer tools to enrich cultural heritage data and related knowledge.

2nd Policy Recommendation

Position the Cloud as a coordination and integration layer

The Cloud should act as a coordination and integration layer that connects and aligns existing initiatives rather than duplicates or centralises them. Its role is to enable complementarity between actors and initiatives, providing a shared operational space where workflows, methodologies, and reference services can converge, while preserving the autonomy and identity of contributing institutions and infrastructures.

Governance levels: EU

Several **research and technology infrastructures** provide key resources and services that can directly or indirectly benefit cultural heritage professionals. While the ECHOES project already involves the most active ERICs in the field and provides a dedicated space for collaboration, there is no such platform for **AI Factories** focused on cultural heritage. The Cultural Heritage Cloud should develop an ecosystem-wide partnership with AI Factories on cultural heritage data, tools and capacity building.

The success of producing and sharing new knowledge within Digital Commons relies on communities. Within the Cloud ecosystem and governance, communities should have a deciding voice and agency over their work. As detailed in the ECHOES Community Building Strategy, **umbrella organisations**, such as ICOM, ICOMOS, E.C.C.O, NEMO, Michael Culture Association or APEF, play a crucial role in establishing a network of collaboration and trust and will have a dedicated meeting place within future Cloud governance to steer strategic decisions. Together with regional and local authorities, they are also strategically placed to engage directly with local cultural heritage institutions, innovation hubs, and citizens and help them navigate the digital turn.

3rd

Policy Recommendation

Promote ecosystem-based governance and stakeholder engagement

Governance should adopt an ecosystem-based, or commons-based, governance approach that ensures structured participation of cultural heritage institutions, research and data infrastructures, umbrella organisations, regional and local authorities and citizen-oriented networks. Mechanisms for stakeholder engagement and co-creation should be embedded in the governance model.

Governance levels: EU, national, regional/local, institutional

1.3 Future competences in a changing world

The study, conservation, and valorisation of cultural heritage are very active fields in Europe. Cultural heritage itself is also evolving alongside social, cultural, and environmental changes. These changes must be taken into account when planning and designing the Cloud governance and deployment, and more generally in the governance of the field within Europe.

Strategic foresight is necessary to anticipate these changes. “Anticipating Futures for Heritage”, the ICCROM Foresight Initiative Horizon Scan Study 2021⁵ identified key political, environmental, technological, and economic trends that will affect how cultural heritage is preserved, perceived, and used by different communities. “Technological trends” include rapid development of new technologies, the growing volume and diversity of born and hybrid digital heritage, increasing cybersecurity threats, and misalignment between private-sector technologies and the public mission of cultural heritage institutions.

⁵ Wollentz, G. (2021) “Anticipating Futures for Heritage: ICCROM Foresight Initiative Horizon Scan Study 2021”.

At the research and innovation level, the Partnership on Resilient Cultural Heritage and its Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (ARCHE SRIA)⁶ provide the principal framework for aligning European research priorities with heritage conservation, climate adaptation, and community resilience. The ARCHE SRIA in particular identifies the governance of heritage data and digital infrastructure as a cross-cutting priority, making it directly relevant to the strategic design of the Cloud and its long-term institutional arrangements.

These priorities are reflected in the ECCCH Strategic and Research Agenda, which was built on these previous exercises, and a foresight exercise carried out with ECHOES. This agenda describes the vision and mission of the Cultural Heritage Cloud, which will serve as a basis for anticipating relevant trends and proposing adaptation strategies.

The Cultural Heritage Cloud should help its stakeholders and members navigate those changes through agile, participatory governance. The continuation of joint, European, and international-level foresight alongside other relevant initiatives is key to positioning Cultural Heritage Digital Commons as a driver of positive change. This aforementioned ICCROM Foresight Initiative calls for cultural heritage to *“inspire new ways of thinking and to protect human rights and deliver equity and social justice; combat climate change and environmental degradation; acknowledge diverse perspectives, knowledge and expertise; strengthen communities to be adaptable and resilient to future changes; develop new technologies that are ethical and humane; and promote inclusive wealth for all.”*

This vision highlights opportunities for the Cultural Heritage Cloud to have a positive impact on communities. These opportunities include innovative collaborative production of knowledge about cultural heritage, increased professional and public digital cultural heritage literacy, improved conservation workflows, improved digital tools, increased transnational collaboration, etc.

The development of the Cultural Heritage Cloud initiative must help cultural heritage institutions, research performing organisations, and cultural and creative industries to not only build technical capacity, but also institutional and governance capacity to promote the values of open, collaborative digital cultural heritage. In some cases, this may require clarification or redefinition of competencies and internal governance workflows to adapt to new tools, methods and international environment and requires constant dialogue with policymakers and industry leaders.

⁶ ARCHE Consortium (2025) *ARCHE SRIA and its Synthesis*.

Informing public and private decision-makers in our field is a crucial task for the future Cultural Heritage Cloud governance. This must be done based on scientific evidence, exchange of good practices, and robust community participation mechanisms. To do this, the Cloud will collaborate with partner initiatives such as the Partnership on Resilient cultural heritage and research infrastructures, which place impact assessment, foresight and scientific dialogue with policymakers at the core of their activities.

4th Policy Recommendation

Strengthen long-term sustainability through foresight

The Cultural Heritage Cloud governance should remain adaptable and flexible to digital, technical and societal changes by integrating strategic foresight as a structural component of its governance.

It should be performed in coordination with researchers, cultural heritage professionals, and relevant policy platforms active in the field and adjacent areas. It should feed both the Cloud's strategic agenda and the dialogue with European institutions.

Governance levels: EU, national, regional/local, institutional

In addition, accessibility is a priority for the Cultural Heritage Cloud, which aims to be fully and independently available to users with disabilities. In accordance with the priorities of the 2026 European Commission communication on 'Enhancing the strategy for the rights of persons with disabilities up to 2030',⁷ the Cultural Heritage Cloud will use accessibility standards as one of its frames of reference for its adaptation strategy to future technical and technological evolutions.

Together, informed and forward-looking cultural heritage actors must defend the role of cultural heritage as a common good with direct and indirect positive impact on social wellbeing, scientific and economic growth, and sense of place. Cultural heritage must remain a federative and driving force in European and national policies, at a moment when Europe faces important challenges.

⁷ European Commission (2026) *Enhancing the Strategy for the Rights of Persons with Disabilities up to 2030*.

5th

Policy Recommendation

Invest in capacity-building and inclusive participation

Capacity building should be treated as a core function of the Cloud, enabling smaller institutions and less-resourced actors to effectively participate. This includes training, technical support, and accessible tools, while ensuring inclusive participation across countries, regions, institution types, and user groups, with attention to multilingualism, digital divides, and local engagement.

Governance levels: EU, national, regional/local, institutional

2. “Meaningful interoperability”: sharing technical norms, concepts, and objectives

The vision of the Cultural Heritage Cloud on “meaningful interoperability” goes beyond interoperability as a technical property of systems. It is a governance commitment that includes the deliberate alignment of standards, concepts, and community-driven values to enable and facilitate the exchange of cultural heritage data, knowledge, and resources across institutions, sectors, and borders, while preserving cultural diversity and scientific excellence.

Meaningful interoperability builds on existing national, European and international initiatives and standards, which provide layers of organisational, semantic and technological dimensions and resources. The Cultural Heritage Cloud governance aims to connect these dimensions with operational mechanisms and resources that align with community sociotechnical needs, concepts and objectives.

2.1 Shared norms, concepts and values

As highlighted by the NGI Commons project report titled “From Open Access to Collective Governance⁸,” European policies have gradually shifted their focus from supporting open access to digital resources to promoting collective and collaborative governance and management of Digital Commons.

The Cultural Heritage Cloud’s approach to meaningful interoperability embraces this paradigm shift fully. Beyond necessary – and complex – technical interoperability between cultural heritage data and tools, the Cloud governance should contribute to establishing a “common layer” of conceptual, normative and strategic objectives to steer the development and use of its future ecosystem.

Conceptual interoperability within the Cultural Heritage Cloud is supported by the Heritage Digital Twin Ontology (HDTO). Based on common grounds created by CIDOC CRM (ISO 21127:2023) and developed within ECHOES together with the ECCCH sister projects, the HDTO provides a shared framework for working on heritage entities, digital representations, provenance, interpretative narratives and knowledge-production workflows, while remaining extensible for domain-specific communities.

Based on existing frameworks in the field of cultural heritage and open science communities, the Cultural Heritage Cloud normative principles guide the creation and promotion of interoperability guidelines and requirements. These common principles — openness, FAIR, trust, accountability, respect for cultural rights, non-discrimination, sustainability — are aligned with the European Declaration on Digital Rights and Principles and with the Culture Compass for Europe and provide solid grounds for collaborating with partners who share the same values. These founding principles are further described in Deliverable 10.1 of the ECHOES project⁹.

Sharing cultural heritage and digital concepts and values is often insufficient to achieve meaningful interoperability. To collaborate within the Cultural Heritage Cloud, communities need shared objectives. Cultural heritage preservation, accessibility, reuse, scientific integrity, democratic participation and long-term stewardship ensure that technical interoperability translates into genuine collaboration and collective value creation.

⁸ Krewer J. (2025) “From Open Access to Collective Governance – Two Decades of Digital Commons Policies in the European Union”.

⁹ Pollé, A., et al. (2025) *Founding principles of the Cloud Governance (D10.1)*.

Without these shared reference points, technical bridges between digital systems risk producing data flows, tools and resources that are operationally valid but semantically, legally, or ethically misaligned and that will fail to meet the Cultural Heritage Cloud vision for Digital Commons.

6th

Policy Recommendation

Enhance data usability and knowledge transformation

The Cultural Heritage Cloud should prioritise norms and concepts, and all related tools, services, and workflows that help transform data into actionable knowledge for conservation, research, education, public engagement, and evidence-based policymaking.

Recommended frameworks should “place the heritage objects at [their] core, while integrating digital technologies as complementary tools that generate tangible benefits for heritage access, understanding and preservation”¹⁰, as well as “Stimulate dissemination and access to open data by using data as a common framework for studying heritage objects and the sciences examining them”¹¹.

Governance levels: EU, national, regional/local, institutional

2.2 Smart standardisation

As a concept, interoperability does not mean “one-size-fits-all”. Differences in understanding, interpretation, and scientific and ethical approaches can improve the development of innovative tools and holistic knowledge of cultural heritage. Meaningful interoperability thrives on these differences, which bring value to collaborating within the Cultural Heritage Cloud.

¹⁰ Demetrescu, E., Cano, E., Goulet, A.-M., Barbot, M. S., Calcerano, F., De Luca, L., Garcia, J., Pedrazzi, T., & Saintenoy, T. (2025). Cultural Heritage Position paper - European research challenges: CNR, CNRS, CSIC Humanities & Social Sciences Scientific perspectives. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17533725>

¹¹ Ibid.

The Cloud understands “smart standardisation” as a common, open baseline combined with managed variation across domains and communities. Concretely, this involves:

- A core of open standards and reference profiles — persistent identifiers, metadata schemas, APIs, ontologies, security and provenance models — aligned with EOSC and the data space for cultural heritage.
- Domain-specific extensions and mappings, so that archaeology, conservation science, archival description or intangible heritage (for example) retain their methodological distinctiveness while remaining connectable through documented crosswalks.
- Adaptive governance of standards, with regular multistakeholder review involving technical experts, heritage professionals and user communities, so that norms evolve in response to new technologies (AI, distributed ledgers), ethical challenges and policy priorities.
- A progressive onboarding, allowing institutions with different levels of digital maturity — from national research infrastructures to small local museums — to join and contribute without centralised gatekeeping.

This strategy of smart standardisation for the Cultural Heritage Cloud is fully in line with the principles of open standards promoted by CIDOC CRM and other similar initiatives working towards a shared understanding of cultural heritage data. It is a fundamental part of the integration strategy of the ECHOES project, which aims to “[find] a balance between standardisation and orchestration” (D3.1 - Integration strategy).

7th Policy Recommendation

Develop meaningful interoperability frameworks

Interoperability should be approached beyond technical standards, incorporating shared concepts, governance practices, and organisational alignment.

Flexible and adaptive frameworks should be prioritised over rigid standardisation models, ensuring inclusiveness across diverse actors and contexts.

Governance levels: EU, national

2.3 Public-private partnerships within Digital Commons

Meaningful interoperability is also an approach to creating the right conditions for different types of actors and sectors to collaborate. The Cultural Heritage Cloud is an open-source initiative. As such, it recognises open source as a public good, as a major driver of scientific innovation and as a key contributor to European economic competitiveness, as demonstrated by the literature.¹²

Large open-source initiatives, such as the Linux Foundation, provide examples for future Cultural Heritage Cloud governance on how to create successful public-private partnerships for the Cultural Heritage Digital Commons. Many open-source digital heritage tools were developed, fully or partially, within such partnerships. This includes the development of several of the future ECCCH tools within ECHOES and the sister projects.

As described in the ECCCH SRIA,¹³ we believe that the Cultural Heritage Cloud vision and mission for Digital Commons will benefit from the involvement of private companies across the digital, heritage, and broader cultural sectors – and they will benefit from that vision too.

Meaningful interoperability provides a concrete basis for structuring public-private partnerships (PPPs) that reinforce the Digital Commons, by:

- Distinguishing contractually between the commons layer — standards, core ontologies, reference software, shared datasets, governed under public or community oversight — and the service layer, where private partners can innovate and compete.
- Making interoperability-by-design a precondition for participation in the Cultural Heritage Cloud, including data and model portability, absence of unjustified lock-in and compliance with the Data Act's provisions on cloud switching.
- Embedding safeguards for public values, including respect for intellectual property, cultural diversity, community rights, ethical AI use (AI Act¹⁴) and long-term preservation, into procurement and service level agreements.

¹² Blind, K., Böhm, M., Grzegorzewska, P., Katz, A., Muto, S., Pätsch, S. and Schubert, T. (2021) *The impact of Open Source Software and Hardware on technological independence, competitiveness and innovation in the EU economy*. Brussels: Final Study Report.

¹³ Demestrescu, E., et al. (2026) *ECCCH's Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (D11.1)*.

¹⁴ European Parliament (2024) *Regulation laying down harmonised rules on artificial intelligence*.

8th

Policy Recommendation

Strengthen long-term sustainability through hybrid funding models

To ensure long-term viability, the Cultural Heritage Cloud should rely on diversified and hybrid funding mechanisms, that combine EU programme support, national co-funding, regional development funds, carefully framed in-kind or service contributions from participating institutions and partners, and potentially private contributions.

Sustainability strategies should reflect the non-profit nature of many cultural heritage institutions and ensure accessibility. Funding strategies should also account for the full life cycle of digital assets and be scale-adaptive, recognising that the resources required vary significantly between monumental ensembles, single artefacts, intangible expressions, and digital-born heritage.

Governance levels: EU, national, regional/local, institutional

3. Digital and cultural sovereignty: promoting shared values through norms

The Cultural Heritage Cloud governance will operate in a complex international environment, where democratic values are often challenged, and cybersecurity threats have increased significantly. Digital Commons can help address these challenges by increasing resilience and creating a community-protected ecosystem based on open norms.

3.1 Promoting open norms

The European Union is often referred to in the literature as “normative power”. This concept refers to the Union's capacity to govern through the diffusion of norms grounded in openness rather than through coercive or protectionist measures. This capacity to elaborate and promote both values and technical norms within and outside Europe, and to inspire their voluntary adoption by stakeholders outside of its direct jurisdiction. This capacity to influence diverse stakeholders on a diverse range of issues is often called the “Brussels effect”.

While cultural policy remains a supporting competence of the European Union, digital sovereignty has emerged as a cross-cutting objective embedded across data governance, competition law, and digital regulation. In this context, the Union's capacity to act lies in its ability to structure openness through coherent legal and normative frameworks. The success and limitations of this approach are particularly evident in the digital field, where the European Union is a key normative body on the global stage, yet European companies and initiatives often struggle to compete with other global players.

The Digital Commons approach requires moving beyond framing openness as a paradox and instead recognising that, while openness is a foundational European value, it requires effective governance to remain sustainable and equitable. If left entirely unregulated, large open systems such as the Cultural Heritage Cloud can create structural dependencies and power imbalances, particularly where dominant platforms and non-European standards shape digital and cultural ecosystems.

This is especially salient in the field of culture and cultural heritage, which constitute cornerstones of what it means to be European. In this domain, European values serve as foundational principles guiding the governance and management of heritage and culture. Citizens legitimately expect that ethical considerations are embedded in the processes and practices related to cultural heritage, as these practices directly shape the foundations of European identity and social cohesion.

To address the challenges of “governing openness”, safeguards such as interoperability requirements, transparency, public oversight, and long-term stewardship have been implemented into both binding and non-binding instruments, including the Digital Services Act, the Data Governance Act, and related policy frameworks.

This approach should guide the development of Cultural Heritage Digital Commons. The Cultural Heritage Cloud and its partners should be seen not only as data or service providers, but as vectors and guarantors of open norms and values.

They must ensure that access to and reuse of cultural data and services are governed in accordance with the fundamental values of the European Union and its aims, understood as the normative principles recognised in Union law and policy that justify collective action in the public interest, including democracy, cultural diversity, solidarity, accessibility, and intergenerational responsibility.

In the field of cultural heritage, these values frame cultural assets, including their digital existence, as common goods whose preservation, accessibility, and governance serve society as a whole, rather than private interests, thereby legitimising public funding, cross-border cooperation, and EU-level governance structures. Cultural Heritage Digital Commons must promote this value-driven approach and, in doing so, will support the promotion of fundamental rights and the European open normative approach to governance at a global scale.

9th

Policy Recommendation

Promote Cultural Heritage Digital Commons within EU policy frameworks and strategic priorities

The development of an open collaborative environment and its governance within the Cultural Heritage Cloud should be explicitly embedded in key EU policy frameworks, including the Culture Compass and digital strategies.

The Cloud should promote EU open norms as a global model. Greater coherence across initiatives is needed to maximise impact and avoid fragmentation, positioning cultural heritage as a strategic domain within European policy. The Cloud should therefore formalise governance links with EOSC and the data space for cultural heritage.

Governance levels: EU

3.2 Reinforcing cultural heritage data sovereignty

Digital Sovereignty has become an important, albeit contested, conceptual framework that often guides how digital actors, including state and non-state actors, in different regions of the world, govern the development and use of digital resources¹⁵.

In this policy brief, we define cultural heritage data sovereignty as the capacity of public authorities, cultural institutions, and communities to retain meaningful control over the collection, governance, access, and reuse of their cultural heritage data, in accordance with public values and legal standards and in pursuit of the public interest objective of the safeguarding of cultural heritage.

In the last decade, digital sovereignty has become a strategic priority for the European Union and several of its Member States¹⁶. Cultural heritage data sovereignty, as proposed by the Cultural Heritage Cloud, is aligned with the principles of the Data Governance Act.¹⁷ While the Act provides specific exclusions for cultural heritage institutions to protect third-party rights, its broader framework for trusted data sharing, intermediary neutrality, and interoperability serves as a vital blueprint for reinforcing sovereignty and preventing dominant private actors from capturing public-interest data.

In practice, this entails the Cultural Heritage Cloud to prioritise Europe-based infrastructures, fostering public-public and public-private partnerships grounded in open standards, and embedding ethical and legal safeguards, including respect for intellectual property rights, cultural diversity, and community rights. The Cultural Heritage Cloud should serve as a strategic instrument in this regard, enabling a federated, secure environment where data sovereignty is exercised collectively without undermining openness, innovation, or cross-border collaboration.

- **Clarifying roles across governance levels:** reinforcing data sovereignty starts with a clear division of responsibilities. Cultural heritage remains primarily a national competence, carried out by institutions, regions and national authorities, while the EU plays a supporting and coordinating role in culture, research and digital policy. The Cultural Heritage Cloud should therefore act as an enabler, not an additional layer of complexity: its purpose is to connect local, regional, national and European actors and to make their efforts more complementary.

¹⁵ Santaniello, M. (2026) "Attributes of Digital Sovereignty: A Conceptual Framework".

¹⁶ Pohle, J. & Thiel, T. (2020) "Digital sovereignty".

¹⁷ European Parliament (2022) *Regulation on European data governance*.

- **A transnational dimension:** data sovereignty in cultural heritage is inherently transnational. European heritage data circulates in an environment shaped by international conventions, global platforms and cross-border research collaborations. The Cultural Heritage Cloud should therefore position itself as a normative reference, promoting open, interoperable and rights-based standards that can be taken up well beyond its own membership. By aligning with EOSC and the common European data space for cultural heritage, and by engaging international partners, it can contribute to a global ecosystem in which data is shared under conditions that respect provenance, custodianship and community rights.
- **Sovereignty as governed openness:** in this sense, data sovereignty does not mean closure. It means shaping openness — through shared rules, standards and safeguards — so that it consistently serves public values and long-term stewardship. The Culture Compass provides a strategic framework for evidence-based cultural governance, including an EU cultural data hub and regular reporting on the state of culture. The Cultural Heritage Cloud and its data-sovereignty arrangements should feed into and draw from this framework, ensuring that heritage data contributes to the wider EU cultural knowledge base while remaining governed by clear public-interest safeguards

In the run for the consolidation of a European digital sovereignty, private actors have also played – and continue to play – a fundamental role. Indeed, they have often been a source of inspiration for public policies on digital matters or have played a significant part in implementing them, thanks to either their self-regulation or their direct participation in decision-making bodies (Farrand, B. and Carrapico, H. (2022))¹⁸. With the ever-increasing place of digital technologies in politics, diplomacy and governance and the new threats faced by European data stored and exploited on non-European platforms, the public and private sectors now have shared concerns and interests to reinforce and protect European digital sovereignty by developing tools and services compliant with EU standards, such as the Cultural Heritage Cloud.

¹⁸ Farrand, B. and Carrapico, H. (2022) “Digital sovereignty and taking back control: from regulatory capitalism to regulatory mercantilism in EU cybersecurity”.

3.3 Towards a Global Digital Commons for Cultural Heritage data

The Cultural Heritage Cloud is conceived as a cornerstone of a broader global Digital Commons for cultural heritage data. This common is not a single platform but an ecosystem of infrastructures, standards, communities, and practices that enable the co-creation, sharing, and reuse of heritage data across borders and sectors under governance rules that prioritise public interest, inclusiveness, and sustainability. Within this vision, the Cloud must look beyond project and membership boundaries and act as a normative and interoperable node within a global network of digital heritage initiatives.

Moving towards a global Digital Commons requires deliberate partnerships with like-minded initiatives inside and outside the EU. Within Europe, this means deepening cooperation with the common European data space for cultural heritage, EOSC, and relevant research infrastructures (including ERICs in heritage science and the humanities, or in other relevant fields for cultural heritage), to align standards, co-develop reference ontologies, and coordinate approaches to long-term preservation, rights management, and ethical data use. Beyond Europe, collaboration with international organisations, regional heritage networks, and global platforms can support the diffusion of EU-based open norms while integrating diverse perspectives and knowledge traditions. The emphasis should be on interoperability-by-design rather than institutional expansion.

A commons-based approach also reframes public–private cooperation. Many tools and services used by heritage institutions are provided by private actors whose business models rely on open standards and shared data resources. By structuring the Cloud as a common, one can formulate clear conditions under which private partners contribute to and benefit from shared infrastructures—covering interoperability obligations, openness of core standards, and respect for public values. This helps mitigate lock-in risks and asymmetrical dependencies, while channelling innovation and investment towards collectively defined priorities.

10th**Policy Recommendation****Strengthen European cultural and digital sovereignty**

The Cloud should contribute to European cultural and digital sovereignty by reducing dependency on external platforms and mitigating risks of data appropriation by non-European actors. A balanced approach is required to reconcile openness with strategic autonomy, addressing the “paradox of openness”.

The Cloud should also contribute to embedding cultural heritage into regional digital strategies, as well as leveraging local innovation ecosystems.

Governance levels: EU, national

4. Conclusion

The Cultural Heritage Cloud represents an important opportunity to organise European digital cultural heritage around a shared, open and collaborative framework – the Cultural Heritage Digital Commons. Its purpose should not be to replace existing institutions or competencies, but to make them work better together. For this reason, its governance must be based on subsidiarity, recognising the responsibilities of local, regional, national and European actors, while creating the conditions for stronger coordination across them.

The discussions reflected in this policy brief show that cultural heritage data cannot be governed only through technical solutions. Interoperability is essential, but it must be meaningful. This means that common standards, ontologies and tools should be connected to shared values, clear objectives and the practical needs of heritage communities. A balanced approach is therefore needed: sufficiently common to allow cooperation across borders and sectors, but flexible enough to respect the diversity of disciplines, institutions and cultural contexts.

The Cloud can also contribute to a stronger understanding of digital and cultural sovereignty. In this field, sovereignty should not mean restricting access or limiting reuse. Rather, it should mean governing openness in a way that protects public values, supports long-term stewardship and prevents dependency on closed or non-transparent systems. Open standards, public oversight, ethical safeguards and community participation are therefore central to the future governance of the Cloud.

By working closely with initiatives such as the European Open Science Cloud, the common European Data Space for Cultural Heritage, the Europeana initiative, and relevant research infrastructures, the Cultural Heritage Cloud can become a key contributor to the creation of cultural heritage Digital Commons in Europe. Its long-term success will depend on its capacity to remain useful, trusted and responsive to the communities it serves.

Ultimately, the Cloud should help ensure that digital transformation strengthens cultural heritage as a common good. If governed in an inclusive, transparent and forward-looking way, it can support more resilient institutions, richer knowledge production and a more democratic and inclusive circulation of cultural heritage data, tools and resources in Europe and beyond.

5. List of policy recommendations

Based on the first two ECHOES Policy events and the related work within the project, this policy brief recommends to all interested parties the following:

1

Structure the Cultural Heritage Cloud governance as a multi-level governance framework for Cultural Heritage Digital Commons

EU, national, regional/local, institutional

2

Position the Cloud as a coordination and integration layer

EU

3

Promote ecosystem-based governance and stakeholder engagement

EU, national, regional/local, institutional

4

Strengthen long-term sustainability through foresight

EU, national, regional/local, institutional

5

Invest in capacity-building and inclusive participation

EU, national, regional/local, institutional

6

Enhance data usability and knowledge transformation

EU, national, regional/local, institutional

7

Develop meaningful interoperability frameworks

EU, national

8

Strengthen long-term sustainability through hybrid funding models

EU, national, regional/local, institutional

9

Promote Cultural Heritage Digital Commons within EU policy frameworks and strategic priorities

EU

10

Strengthen European cultural and digital sovereignty

EU, national

References

Allsop, D. B., Chelladurai, J. M., Kimball, E. R., Marks, L. D., & Hendricks, J. J. (2022) "Qualitative methods with Nvivo software: A practical guide for analysing qualitative data", *Psych*, 4(2), 142-159.

ARCHE Consortium (2025) *ARCHE SRIA and its Synthesis*.

Bakirtzis, N., Soyluoglu, M., *et al.* (2026) *Strategy for community building (D4.2)*. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.20443314

Blind, K., Böhm, M., Grzegorzewska, P., Katz, A., Muto, S., Pätsch, S. and Schubert, T. (2021) *The impact of Open Source Software and Hardware on technological independence, competitiveness and innovation in the EU economy: Final Study Report*.

Council Resolution on the EU Work Plan for Culture 2023–2026 2022/C 466/01.

Demetrescu, E., *et al.* (2026) *ECCCH's Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (D11.1)*. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.20447414

Demetrescu, E., Cano, E., Goulet, A.-M., Barbot, M. S., Calcerano, F., De Luca, L., Garcia, J., Pedrazzi, T., & Saintenoy, T. (2025). Cultural Heritage Position paper - European research challenges: CNR, CNRS, CSIC Humanities & Social Sciences Scientific perspectives. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17533725>

ECHOES and Europeana (2026), "Joint Statement from the Europeana Initiative and the ECHOES project on the complementarity between the common European data space for cultural heritage and the European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage".

European Commission (2025), Communication *A Culture Compass for Europe*.

European Commission (2026), Communication *Enhancing the strategy for the rights of persons with disabilities up to 2030*.

European Working Team on Digital Commons (2022) *Towards a Sovereign Digital Infrastructure of Commons: Report of the European Working Team on Digital Commons*.

Farrand, B. and Carrapico, H. (2022) "Digital sovereignty and taking back control: from regulatory capitalism to regulatory mercantilism in EU cybersecurity", *European Security*, 31(3), pp. 435–453. doi: [10.1080/09662839.2022.2102896](https://doi.org/10.1080/09662839.2022.2102896).

Gioia, D. (2021) "A systematic methodology for doing qualitative research", *The Journal of Applied Behavioural Science*, 57(1), 20-29.

Kotzinos, D., Chambers, S., Barbot, L., Ďurčo, M., & Dalla Torre, G. (2025) *ECHOES Integration Strategy for datasets, tools and workflows with potential for reuse in ECHOES (D3.1)*. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17751335>.

Krewer J. (2025) "From Open Access to Collective Governance – Two Decades of Digital Commons Policies in the European Union". Available at: <https://www.europeanheritagehub.eu/document/from-open-access-to-collective-governance-two-decades-of-digital-commons-policies-in-the-european-union/>.

Mayring, P. (2015) "Qualitative Content Analysis: Theoretical Background and Procedures", in Bikner-Ahsbals, A., Knipping, C., Presmeg, N. (eds) *Approaches to Qualitative Research in Mathematics Education. Advances in Mathematics Education*. doi: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-017-9181-6_13.

Mortelmans, D. (2025) "Doing qualitative data analysis with NVivo", *Springer Nature*, p. 282.

Niccolucci F. et al. (2023) "The Heritage Digital Twin: a bicycle made for two", *Open Research Europe*. doi: <https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.15496.1>.

Petitcol, R., et al. (2026) *Governance Model of the legal entity (D10.2)*. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.20446838

Pohle, J. & Thiel, T. (2020) "Digital sovereignty", *Internet Policy Review*, 9(4). doi: <https://doi.org/10.14763/2020.4.1532>.

Polat, A. (2025) "Thematic analysis in qualitative research: Common pitfalls and practical insights for academic writing", *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*, 24. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1177/160940692513728>.

Pollé, A., et al. (2025) *ECHOES Founding principles of the Cloud Governance (D10.1)*. Available at: <https://zenodo.org/records/17599162>.

Regulation (EU) 2022/868 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 May 2022 on European data governance and amending Regulation (EU) 2018/1724 (Data Governance Act).

Regulation (EU) 2022/2065 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 19 October 2022 on a Single Market for Digital Services and amending Directive 2000/31/EC (Digital Services Act).

Santaniello, M. (2026) "Attributes of Digital Sovereignty: A Conceptual Framework", *Geopolitics*, 31(2), pp. 788–809. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1080/14650045.2025.2521548>.

Srivastava, P., & Hopwood, N. (2009) "A practical iterative framework for qualitative data analysis", *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*, 8(1), 76-84.

Wollentz, G. (2023) "Anticipating Futures for Heritage: ICCROM Foresight Initiative Horizon Scan Study 2021," *Anticipating Futures for Heritage: ICCROM Foresight Initiative Horizon Scan Study 2021*.

Annex 1: ECHOES Policy Events

First ECHOES Policy Event – 12-13 December 2024 – Brussels, Belgium

Figure 1: ECHOES Coordinator Xavier RODIER presenting the project during first ECHOES Policy Event

The first ECHOES Policy Event was held over two half-days on 12 and 13 December 2024 at the Royal Institute for cultural heritage (KIK-IRPA) in Brussels, Belgium.

Sixty people attended the Event in person, and over three hundred online.

12 December 2024

On the first afternoon, 12 December, participants were welcomed by Hilde DE CLERCQ, General Director of KIK-IRPA, and heard addresses by Marc LEMAITRE (Director-General, DG RTD), Chris DE LOOF (Innovation Manager, BELSPO/BELNET), Lionel MAUREL (Scientific Deputy Director, CNRS Sciences Humaines et Sociales), and Costanza MILIANI (ISPC Director, CNR).

Xavier RODIER, Coordinator of ECHOES, presented the project, and was followed by a keynote speech given by Bart FRANSEN titled ‘Studying Jan van Eyck on a laptop, Results from the VERONA project (Van Eyck Research in Open Access)’.

The round table of the afternoon was chaired by Philippe VENDRIX (CNRS) and gathered Pascal LIEVAUX (French Ministry of Culture), Sophie CUMMINGS (UKRI), Eva STENSKOLD (Swedish National Data Service) and Rickard BUCKSCH (DG RTD) around the theme 'Establishing a multi-level governance for the Cultural Heritage Cloud'. The day was wrapped up by a networking cocktail.

13 December 2024

On 13 December, the Policy Event carried on with a workshop on onboarding communities into the Cultural Heritage Cloud. Emanuel DEMETRESCU (CNR) gave the introduction speech, focused on the added value of the Cultural Heritage Cloud over time through asset reuse, community-led onboarding and Knowledge Graphs as connective tissue of the ecosystem; the framework presented on that occasion was further developed in the ECCCH SRIA (D11.1).

A roundtable titled 'Working on cultural heritage in a Digital Age', moderated by Adeline JOFFRES (CNRS) occupied the first half of the morning, with participants Franco NICCOLUCCI (ARIADNE RI), Harry VERWAYEN (Europeana Foundation), Corinne SZTEINSZNAIDER (Michael Culture Association), Darja FISER (CLARIN ERIC) and Vania Virgili (E-RIHS) sharing their experiences.

Two presentations followed, one on the ECHOES Consultation by Rémi PETITCOL (FSP), and one on the ECHOES Cascading Grants by Sally CHAMBERS (DARIAH ERIC), and an interactive session on how to get involved rounded up a successful event.

Figure 2: First ECHOES Policy Event, 12 Dec. 2024 roundtable

Second ECHOES Policy Event – 5 February 2026 – Brussels, Belgium

Figure 3: Audience at second ECHOES Policy Event

The second ECHOES Policy Event was held on 5 February 2026 at the Maison Irène et Frédéric Joliot-Curie in Brussels, Belgium.

Sixty-two people attended the Event in person, and over a hundred followed online.

The day was kicked off by the welcome address given by Fabrice BOUDJAABA (CNRS Sciences Humaines et Sociales Director), and the inspiring words of esteemed guests Joanna DRAKE (DG RTD Deputy Director General 'Planet, People and Science for Policy'), Katja REPPPEL (DG RTD Head of Unit 'Democracy, Equality and Culture'), Christian EHLER (MEP) and Anne BESNIER (CoR).

Following this introduction, Xavier RODIER (ECHOES Coordinator) and Dimitris KOTZINOS (CY Cergy-Paris Université/CNRS) gave a general presentation of the project and its advancements, and Philippe VENDRIX (CNRS) presented the Sustainability stakes and strategy for the Cultural Heritage Cloud.

The keynote of the day was given by Alexandre CAUSSE and Mariachiara ESPOSITO (FSP) on the recently funded European Partnership Resilient cultural heritage.

In the afternoon, two roundtables highlighted crucial challenges in the construction of the Cultural Heritage Cloud governance:

The first roundtable, chaired by Mariachiara ESPOSITO (FSP) gathered Pascal LIEVAUX (French Ministry of Culture), Anne BESNIER (CoR), Rickard BUCKSCH (DG RTD), Manuel GOMEZ HERRERO (DG EAC) and Katerina MOUTOGIANNI (DG CNECT) and explored the themes of multi-level governance and subsidiarity.

The second roundtable was chaired by Philippe VENDRIX (CNRS) and centred on the topic of cooperation in and around the Cloud ecosystem. It brought together representatives of large-scale initiatives Vania VIRGILI (E-RIHS ERIC), Agiatis BENARDOU (DARIAH ERIC), Juliette RAOUL-DUVAL (ICOM Europe), Vincent VANDEGHINSTE (CLARIN ERIC), Harry VERWAYEN (Europeana Foundation) and Franco NICCOLUCCI (ARIADNE RI).

This productive day ended on a high note with a visit of the remains of the Palais du Coudenberg.

Figure 4: MEP Christian EHLER during the second ECHOES Policy Event

Annex 2: Analysis of Policy Insights

Data collection and analysis

The analysis presented in this policy brief summary is based on materials produced within two ECHOES policy events, held in Brussels in December 2024 and February 2026.

These events were designed as structured stakeholder dialogue platforms aimed at discussing the development, governance, and strategic positioning of the European Collaborative Cloud for cultural heritage (ECCCH). They brought together more than 500 participants in Brussels and online, including representatives from European institutions, research infrastructures, cultural heritage organisations (GLAM sector), policymakers, and experts in digital and heritage domains.

The first Policy Event (12–13 December 2024) was organised over two half-days and combined keynote presentations, institutional interventions, and roundtable discussions focusing on the broader context of the Cultural Heritage Cloud and community engagement and onboarding processes.

The second Policy Event (5 February 2026) further developed these discussions, with a specific focus on multi-level governance, subsidiarity, cooperation within the ecosystem, and the future legal and organisational framework of the Cloud. Both events included structured sessions (e.g. keynote speeches and panel discussions) as well as interactive exchanges among stakeholders.

The empirical basis of the analysis consists of qualitative materials generated during these events, including presentation slides and full recordings of the sessions. Where necessary, recordings were reviewed and selectively transcribed to enable systematic textual analysis. These materials capture both formal contributions and interactive exchanges, providing a comprehensive representation of stakeholder perspectives. All materials were systematically collected and organised into a unified textual corpus. Given the heterogeneous and largely unstructured nature of the sources, the analytical objective was to render the content comparable and analytically usable. The corpus was analysed through a qualitative content analysis approach (Mayring, 2014; Mortelmans, 2025), combined with elements of thematic analysis (Polat, 2025).

The analytical strategy followed an inductive–deductive logic. A first coding framework was defined deductively based on the main analytical dimensions guiding the policy brief (e.g. governance, interoperability, sustainability, and digital sovereignty). This was

complemented by an inductive coding phase aimed at identifying themes emerging directly from the discussions. The analytical process followed a hybrid approach combining manual qualitative analysis with structured coding procedures supported by computer-assisted qualitative data analysis software, specifically NVivo. In an initial phase, all materials were manually reviewed to familiarise with the content and identify preliminary themes, key concepts, and relevant analytical dimensions. This exploratory step enabled the identification of first-order categories grounded in stakeholders' contributions. In a second phase, the corpus was organised and systematically coded using NVivo, allowing for the classification, grouping, and retrieval of textual data (Allsop et al., 2022). The coding process followed a structured procedure inspired by established approaches in qualitative research, such as the Gioia methodology (Gioia et al., 2021), which emphasises the progressive organisation of qualitative data from first-order concepts (grounded in participants' language) to second-order themes and aggregate dimensions. In practice, this involved identifying key concepts and expressions within the corpus, grouping them into thematic categories, and progressively structuring them into higher-level analytical domains. The use of NVivo supported the identification of recurring patterns, co-occurrences, and semantic relationships across stakeholder contributions, enabling a more systematic and consistent extraction of insights. Particular attention was given to the recurrence and co-occurrence of key terms, concepts, and problem framings, allowing the identification of patterns of convergence, reflecting shared priorities, as well as divergence, highlighting differences in perspectives, roles, and expectations across actors.

Following the coding phase, the analysis proceeded through a process of thematic clustering and systematisation. Coded elements were aggregated into higher-order categories and synthesised into structured policy insights, ensuring traceability between the original data and the analytical outputs. These insights were then translated into structured analytical formats, including comparative tables, matrices, and conceptual frameworks, allowing for a clearer representation of the relationships between identified challenges, governance needs, and potential policy directions. The overall analytical process followed an iterative logic: emerging insights were continuously refined, regrouped, and validated against the original corpus to ensure coherence with the policy dialogue and to minimise interpretative bias (Srivastava and Hopwood, 2009).

The procedure has been summarised in Figure 1.

Figure 5: Research Methodological Framework (Source: author's elaboration)

2. Main Insights

The analysis of the ECHOES policy events identifies a set of structured and interrelated issues pertaining to the governance, operational dynamics, and strategic positioning of the Cultural Heritage Cloud. As outlined in the previous section, and following the Gioia methodology, first-order concepts derived from verbatim data were systematically aggregated into nine higher-order dimensions. For the purposes of this policy brief, these dimensions are hereafter referred to as “key issues” in order to enhance clarity and accessibility for a broader range of stakeholders. These key issues are synthesised and presented in Table 1 below.

DIMENSION	KEY ISSUE	EVIDENCE FROM POLICY DIALOGUE	IMPLICATION FOR THE CLOUD
Governance	Multi-level coordination gaps	Strong emphasis on EU, national, regional interplay	Need for structured multi-level governance model
Ecosystem	Fragmentation of infrastructures	Multiple initiatives operating in parallel	Cloud as coordination layer
Interoperability	Beyond technical dimension	Need for shared concepts and practices	Develop “meaningful interoperability”
Sustainability	Funding instability	Reliance on project-based funding	Hybrid and long-term funding models
Access	Institutional asymmetries	Smaller institutions face barriers	Capacity-building mechanisms
Data	Underutilisation of data	Data exists but is not fully exploited	Focus on usability and integration
Sovereignty	External control risks	Increasing role of global actors	Strengthen EU data sovereignty
Policy alignment	Fragmented policy landscape	Multiple overlapping EU initiatives	Need for policy coherence
Participation	Uneven engagement	Limited regional involvement	Strengthen inclusiveness

Table 1: Key Insights from Policy Events (Source: authors' elaboration)

For each key issue, the research team identified the relevant analytical dimension and - based on the evidence emerging from the structured policy dialogue - the corresponding implications for the cloud infrastructure. This analytical framework has been deliberately designed to enhance the categorisation and interpretation of issues across core thematic domains (called “dimensions and including governance, ecosystem development, interoperability, sustainability, access, data use, data sovereignty, policy alignment and participation). Such a structured approach enables a more coherent organisation of findings and facilitates the extraction of actionable insights, thereby supporting the formulation of robust and evidence-based policy recommendations presented in this policy brief.

In the following paragraphs, we will further illustrate each aggregate dimension, starting from the domain of reference. To increase readability, we indicated main takeaways for each dimension.

GOVERNANCE

The topic of governance emerged in strict relation to the issue of subsidiarity. In the policy event, participants consistently point to the inherently multi-level nature of cultural heritage governance, which requires coordination across European, national, regional and local government level, as well at the level of institutions. At the same time, the current governance landscape is characterised by an under-integration of regional and local actors, despite their central role in implementation processes and innovation ecosystems. This creates the need for governance arrangements that combine top-down coordination with bottom-up participation, while clarifying roles and responsibilities across levels. The role of umbrella organisations, that foster coordination, networking but also advocacy for cultural heritage, was also discussed.

Main takeaways:

- Cultural heritage governance is inherently multi-level and requires coordination across European, national, regional/local, and institutional actors, as well as with umbrella organisations.
- The current governance landscape shows an under-integration of regional and local, as well as institutional levels, despite their central role in innovation ecosystems.
- Regions play a critical role as intermediaries between policy design and implementation, particularly through smart specialisation strategies.
- Effective governance requires both top-down coordination and bottom-up participation from cultural heritage communities.
- The Cultural Heritage Cloud should function as a coordination mechanism rather than a centralised authority.
- There is a need to clarify roles and responsibilities across governance levels to avoid overlaps and inefficiencies.
- Multi-level governance creates productive tensions that can generate innovation when properly managed.

CH ECOSYSTEM (and COOPERATION)

A second key dimension emerging from the analysis concerns the structure of the cultural heritage ecosystem, which is described as highly fragmented, with multiple infrastructures and initiatives operating in parallel. The insights emphasise that the Cultural Heritage Cloud should not duplicate existing structures, but rather act as a coordination and integration layer, leveraging existing services, data, and expertise.

In this perspective, the value of the Cloud lies in its capacity to foster interconnection, alignment, and cooperation among heterogeneous actors, strengthening a system based on interdependence rather than isolated development. The role of private partners has been discussed, also in relation to the possibility to public-private partnerships for the CH preservation and enhancement.

Main takeaways:

- The European cultural heritage landscape is highly fragmented, requiring stronger coordination among existing initiatives.
- Interconnection and alignment between infrastructures are essential conditions for the success of the Cloud.
- The Cloud should not duplicate existing infrastructures but rather enable complementarities and integration.
- Existing infrastructures already provide critical services, data, and expertise that must be leveraged.
- The value of the Cloud lies in its ability to act as a catalyst for cooperation across heterogeneous actors.
- Shared strategic vision across initiatives needs to be strengthened (e.g. with EOSC or the data space for cultural heritage)
- The ecosystem depends on mutual interdependence between infrastructures rather than isolated development.
- The Cloud must position itself within the existing ecosystem rather than as a competing structure.
- The role of private partners within the digital cultural heritage scenario should be discussed (e.g. public-private partnerships or other forms of collaboration between public and private entities)

INTEROPERABILITY

Interoperability emerges as a central issue, but it is consistently framed as a multidimensional challenge that goes beyond technical aspects. The insights underline the need for shared standards, common frameworks, and shared vocabularies, while also highlighting that standardisation must remain flexible and adaptable to different contexts and to the evolving digital tools and landscapes (e.g. heavily impacted by AI and platformisation of services). Interoperability is therefore understood as a continuous process of alignment among actors, adaptive governance of standards among stakeholders (through discussion among group of experts), rather than a one-time technical solution.

Main takeaways:

- Interoperability is not only technical but also conceptual, organisational, and governance-related
- Shared standards are necessary but must remain flexible and adaptable to different contexts, thus based on an adaptive governance of standards
- A “one-size-fits-all” standardisation approach is not suitable for the cultural heritage domain.
- Interoperability requires continuous alignment between actors (CH organisations with different levels of maturity as well as technical experts and communities), not a one-time technical solution
- Common frameworks, shared norms and shared vocabularies are essential for effective data integration, as well as shared values (e.g. digital cultural heritage as a commons)
- Continuous update is necessary, given the fast-evolving digital scenario (e.g. impact of AI, platformisation, etc...)
- Standardisation should act as a bridge between systems rather than a constraint.

SUSTAINABILITY

Sustainability represents another critical area and is discussed in relation to the future economic model of the Cloud, with strong emphasis on the limitations of current funding models, which are largely based on short-term, project-based schemes. The insights indicate that long-term sustainability depends on the ability of the Cultural Heritage Cloud to demonstrate value and become essential for its users, while also requiring diversified funding approaches and cost structures compatible with the non-profit nature of many cultural institutions.

Main takeaways:

- Long-term sustainability is one of the main unresolved challenges for the Cultural Heritage Cloud.
- Current funding models based on EU programmes are insufficient for long-term infrastructure stability.
- The Cloud must demonstrate clear value and impact to secure sustainable funding.
- Financial sustainability requires diversification of funding sources beyond public funding.
- Many infrastructures face structural fragility due to short-term project-based funding.

- Sustainability is closely linked to the ability of the Cultural Heritage Cloud to demonstrate clear added value, usability, and relevance for its users and stakeholders.
- Cost structures must consider the non-profit nature of many cultural institutions.
- Collaboration between infrastructures can help optimise costs and resources.

ACCESS, INCLUSION & CAPACITY BUILDING

Issues related to access were discussed with reference to inclusion and capacity building, on further highlighting that the main barriers to participation are not purely technological, but institutional and capacity-related. Smaller organisations face significant challenges in accessing and using digital infrastructures, pointing to the need for capacity-building mechanisms, training, and support. At the same time, inclusiveness requires attention to multilingualism and the role of local actors.

Main takeaways:

- The main barrier to participation is not merely technological but also related to organisational capacity, resources, and the ability of institutions to effectively use available tools.
- Smaller institutions face significant challenges in accessing and using digital infrastructures.
- Capacity building is essential for enabling effective participation in the Cloud.
- Tools alone are insufficient without training, support, and guidance.
- Digital divide persists across institutions, regions, and levels of resources.
- Multilingualism is a key requirement for inclusive access.
- Local actors play a fundamental role in ensuring inclusiveness and accessibility.

DATA

The analysis also emphasises the strategic importance of cultural heritage data, which are increasingly recognised as economic and geopolitical assets. A further key dimension emerging from the analysis concerns the use and valorisation of data within the cultural heritage domain. Despite the growing availability of datasets across institutions and infrastructures, the evidence highlights a persistent underutilisation of data, which often remains fragmented, insufficiently curated, or difficult to access and reuse. Policy dialogue participants emphasised that the challenge is not merely the production of additional data, but rather the enhancement of its usability, interoperability, and integration across systems.

In this context, the Cultural Heritage Cloud is expected to play a crucial role in enabling more effective data exploitation by improving discoverability, facilitating access, and supporting advanced analytical and reuse capabilities. Ultimately, the added value of the Cloud lies in transforming existing data into actionable knowledge, fostering innovation, and supporting evidence-based decision-making.

Main takeaways:

- Significant amounts of cultural heritage data already exist but remain underutilised.
- Data fragmentation and limited accessibility hinder effective use.
- Enhanced integration across datasets and platforms is essential.
- The Cloud should facilitate data discoverability and access.
- Interdisciplinary approaches are essential for understanding cultural heritage data.
- The integration of social sciences, humanities, and technology needs to be considered and operationalised in practice.

SOVEREIGNTY

During the discussion, participants addressed concerns related to digital and cultural sovereignty, particularly in relation to the risk of external control by non-European actors and the concentration of cultural content in large private platforms. In this context, the insights highlight the need to balance openness with control, addressing the “paradox of openness” and reinforcing European capacity to manage data production, storage, and access.

- Cultural heritage data is increasingly becoming a strategic economic and geopolitical asset.
- There is a growing risk of cultural heritage content being controlled by non-European private actors.
- The Cultural Heritage Cloud was conceived as a response to this risk.
- European cultural sovereignty requires control over data production, storage, and access.
- The “paradox of openness” highlights the tension between open access and loss of control and could be overcome through a proper governance of openness, that respect provenance but also community rights
- Digital infrastructures are key tools for safeguarding European cultural autonomy.

- Cultural heritage plays a role not only in identity but also in geopolitical positioning.
- The concentration of cultural content in large private platforms poses systemic risks, the role and coordination with private actors is essential

POLICY ALIGNMENT

A minor yet recurrent dimension emerging from the analysis concerns the strategic positioning of the Cultural Heritage Cloud within the broader European Union policy landscape. This theme highlights the growing recognition of the Cloud as a strategic initiative with the potential to contribute to multiple EU policy objectives. The evidence suggests that cultural heritage needs to be integrated into overarching policy frameworks, despite its cross-cutting relevance to domains such as climate action, digital innovation, and social cohesion. In this context, the Cultural Heritage Cloud can play a pivotal role in strengthening policy coherence and alignment, particularly by leveraging existing strategic instruments such as the Culture Compass. Furthermore, the Cloud is positioned to act as an enabling interface between research, policy, and practice, supporting more evidence-based and coordinated policymaking processes across sectors.

Main takeaways:

- The Cultural Heritage Cloud is increasingly recognised as a strategic European policy initiative.
- There is a need to strengthen the integration of cultural heritage within broader EU policy frameworks and align with other initiatives (e.g. EOSC, data space for cultural heritage)
- Cultural heritage is connected to multiple policy domains, including climate, innovation, and social cohesion.
- The Culture Compass provides a key strategic framework for aligning cultural policies.
- Policy coherence across EU initiatives remains a challenge.
- Evidence-based policymaking requires stronger data integration and analysis.
- The Cloud can act as a bridge between research, policy, and practice.

PARTICIPATION

Another dimension emerging from the analysis concerns participation, particularly in relation to the uneven engagement of stakeholders across countries, regions, and institutional contexts. The evidence from the policy dialogue highlights that participation

in cultural heritage initiatives risks remaining asymmetrical, with smaller institutions and certain geographical areas facing structural barriers to involvement.

Limited regional representation and disparities in capacities constrain the inclusiveness of the ecosystem and risk reinforcing existing imbalances. In this context, the Cultural Heritage Cloud is expected to play a key role in broadening participation by lowering access barriers, enabling more equitable engagement, ensuring the protection of openness and community rights and fostering inclusive practices. Strengthening participation is therefore essential not only for fairness, but also for ensuring the diversity, representativeness, and overall effectiveness of the Cloud, towards a global Digital Commons for CH data.

Main takeaways:

- Participation across the cultural heritage ecosystem risks remaining uneven and fragmented.
- Smaller institutions and certain regions face significant barriers to engagement.
- Limited regional involvement could reduce inclusiveness.
- The Cloud should actively promote more inclusive and equitable participation, with the objective of cultural heritage Digital Commons

Concluding remarks

In conclusion, the Cultural Heritage Cloud emerges from the analysis as a fundamentally enabling infrastructure, whose primary role is not to centralise control but to facilitate coordination, integration, and knowledge exchange across a highly heterogeneous landscape. Its added value lies in its capacity to reinforce and connect existing ecosystems, supporting both the production of knowledge and its practical application across research, policy, and professional domains. At the same time, the effectiveness of the Cloud will depend on its ability to strike a careful balance between openness and appropriate governance mechanisms, ensuring trust, reliability, and long-term sustainability. Crucially, its success will be determined not only by its technical robustness but also by its usability, inclusiveness, and relevance to diverse stakeholder communities, including smaller institutions and underrepresented actors. In this perspective, the legitimacy of the Cultural Heritage Cloud is closely tied to its capacity to deliver tangible and widely perceived benefits, fostering engagement and demonstrating clear added value. Rather than disrupting existing structures, the Cloud should position itself as a complementary and integrative layer, capable of enhancing collaboration, reducing fragmentation, and ultimately contributing to a more coherent and resilient European cultural heritage ecosystem.